

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT IN THE HOME LEARNING OF LEARNERS IN THE MODULAR LEARNING MODALITY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 9

Pages: 1009-1024

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2118

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13140358

Manuscript Accepted: 04-06-2024

Parental Involvement in the Home Learning of Learners in the Modular Learning Modality

Asmirah G. Abdulrahman*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The focus of this study was the involvement of parents in the home learning of their children during the modular learning modality. It aimed to describe the experiences, challenges, and coping strategies of parents on their involvement in the home learning of their children during the modular learning modality. The participants of the study were selected (six) 6 parents from the six central schools in the City of Koronadal. They were chosen based on the inclusion criteria: Grade 2 parents whose children received high honors recognition; must be recommended by the adviser and recognized as an active parent. This used a descriptive qualitative research design. Key Informant Interview was utilized in the gathering of data. Parental involvement is important in the learning process of the children. Whatever is the learning modality they have be it face-to-face classes, online classes, and or modular approach, parents should have an involvement in the learning of the children for them to be well guided, well-motivated and well-inspired to learn effectively and efficiently that would cause them to become academically achievers. Their involvement in the home learning of their children is of three aspects, such as: roles, support, and strategies. It is about their involvement in teaching, guiding, motivating the children in learning, and answering the lessons in the modules. In order to guarantee students' learning progress while learning at home, parents must provide a high level of support as learning facilitators. The study is of big help for those parents and guardians who may be going to teach, guide and assist their children in answering their worksheets, performing the tasks in the modules during modular learning modality. Parents served as the ones who get the modules in school; they were second teachers of the learners; they were the motivators for the learners to do all the tasks in the modules; and they were the providers of the additional needed learning materials of the learners. and by doing all those roles and applying strategies in teaching their children, their children still learned during the modular distance learning and had become academic achievers. Schools could encourage the parents involve themselves actively in the home learning of their children even after modular distance learning. They may adapt the strategies of the parent-participants in the study to the teaching of children at home.

Keywords: *parental involvement, home learning of learners, modular learning modality*

Introduction

The covid-19 outbreak has significantly affected people in a variety of ways. This health worldwide danger altered several human functions including education. The lockdowns have had an impact among the 188 countries' and 1,576,021,818 students' lifetimes (UNESCO, 2020) and put forward a challenge on governments that make sure that their learning continues. Schools are no longer open to ensure the staff and students' safety causing the schools worldwide to change the diverse learning from the classroom to the home modalities. Additionally, this has changed how teachers deliver? how pupils are taught, and how parents participate in classroom instruction and learning.

The educational system in the Philippines, one of the nation's most hit by the epidemic, has undergone a profound paradigm shift away from traditional face-to-face instruction and toward various methods of learning delivery, including blended learning and modular distance learning. Studying from home and having physical distance between students and teachers is what distance education, which is very different from traditional education, entails (Sadeghi, 2019).

The Department of Education (DepEd) defines modular distance learning as a method, the utilization of self-learning modules by the teacher (SLMs) to impart the lesson's material to the students at their homes. This technique offers the learners a chance to grow independence and a commitment to accountability in completing the assignments at their own speed and improve their self-study skills over time. Participation in the lessons being taught shown in the SLM. As children study at home, using this learning modality demands a lot of help from parents as facilitators of learning to guarantee advancement in students' learning.

The parents are not trained in fulfilling the tasks of teachers in teaching the children at school, because of the sudden change of face-to-face learning to modular learning modality. Parents have faced a lot of challenges and difficulties in teaching the children at home through the modules. Hence, there was need to conduct a study about it, so that it can help parents who will teach their children using modular distance learning.

Parental involvement in the time of pandemic had become crucial. Parents served as teachers to their children at home. They were the ones who do the tasks of teachers at schools. Modular distance learning is one of the learning delivery modalities that the Department of Education implements. With this, Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) are the main source of learning for the learner. It contains pre-tests, discussion, and a series of evaluations or assessments that the learners need to answer. For learners in lower grades, particularly kinder and grade 1, they need a great extent of support from parents as learning facilitators at home to ensure learners' learning

development or progress. Parents that actively participated in their children's education and emphasized the value of education, according to Huang (as cited in Magouirk, 2015), typically had children whose academic performance improved and whose respect for education increased.

The pandemic has brought a lot of changes in the lives of many, including the education of the Filipino learners especially the early grade pupils particularly from kinder to Grade 3. The support and involvement of parents in the learning process and learning development of their children was mandatorily present. On the other hand, for early grade pupils, they cannot learn how to read, count, and understand the lesson in the modules without the help and guidance of anyone who can facilitate their learnings. Aside from teaching them the lessons in the modules, parents also must give psychosocial intervention to children who have trauma and anxiety due to pandemic. Further, some studies say that parental involvement is essential to a student's academic growth, according to Henderson Berla, 1994; Winters, 1993, parental involvement in their children's education is commonly thought to have a significant impact on their growth and academic success, as well as on school improvement and empowerment.

The study wanted to explore deeply into the experiences of parents on their involvement on the modular distance learning of their children at home. The shift of the learning delivery modalities has brought changes to the given roles and duties of teachers in teaching children in school and to parents at home. By using Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) as the main source of learning today, parents do not just get modules at school and give it to their children at home, but they must act as teachers to their children by teaching, guiding, assisting, motivating, inspiring, counseling, and praising them as they facilitate learning at home. Parents and guardians who fail to do these tasks will have the tendency to have children who have not learned any basic knowledge per subject area in this time of pandemic. This is the case that this study described because it would be of great benefit to the learning development of elementary grade pupils as they are the future of the world. Not all parents are knowledgeable enough to do the tasks of teachers, but they do not have choice but to act as teachers at home for their children to learn even at the hit of pandemic. As stated in the findings of the study of Bonilla, A. H. (2022) that parents have difficulty in facilitating their children at home due to lack of knowledge of the content.

This study described involvement of parents in the home learning of learners during modular distance learning of their children from the experiences of parents from different identified central schools in the Koronadal City Division. Education has transcended the classroom, and parents are now partners with educators. Parents are essential as home facilitators, and their main responsibility in modular learning is to establish a relationship with and provide guidance for their children. Because of this, parents have been given a great deal of responsibility by this learning approach. The Department of Education (DepEd) claims that parents complete a lot of tasks related to modular distance learning.

The purpose of this study was to describe parents' involvement in the home learning of learners at home during MDL in terms of their roles, supports strategies, challenges, and coping strategies and interventions. And the participants of this study will be the grade 2 parents from different identified central schools whose children are studying under modular distance learning.

Research Questions

The study aimed to describe the parental involvement in the home learning of learners during modular distance learning. Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How are the parents involved in the home learning of their children during the modular learning modality in terms of their:
 - 1.1. roles,
 - 1.2. support, and
 - 1.3. strategies?
2. What are the challenges of parents in the home learning of their children during the modular learning modality?
3. What are the coping strategies of parents in the home learning of their children?

Methodology

Research Design

This study is descriptive qualitative research with an interview method. Key Informant Interview (KII) was utilized in the gathering of data needed for the study. It aimed to explore and gain insights from parents who have children who undergo home learning in the modular learning modality.

The general objective of the study was to describe parental involvement in the home learning of learners under the modular learning modality. The results of the study served as the basis for framing the parental involvement program framework.

Participants

The six (6) participants of the study are from the six (6) central schools who were grade 2 parents during the modular distance learning. They were chosen based on the inclusion criteria such as: parent whose child belongs to with honors pupils; identified active and supportive parent; recommended by the adviser; and must be willing to be interviewed. Each parent-participant described as:

Participant 1 is a father from Koronadal Central Elementary School-2 (KCES2). He is a converted to Islam from Waray tribe and he is also a businessman.

Participant 2 is a full-time housewife with 5 children. Her 2nd daughter is studying at Osita Central Elementary School. According to her she really gave full support to the study of her daughter during modular distance learning.

Participant 3 is a mother and a government employee. She has only 1 daughter who is studying at Koronadal Central Elementary School-1 (KCES1). She was identified as the most active and cooperative parent during modular distance learning.

Participant 4 is also a full-time housewife from Marbel 5 Central Elementary School (M5CES). She is one of the participative and active parents of grade 2 parents.

Participant 5 is also a full-time housewife and a mother of three (3) children. Her youngest is studying from Marbel 7 Central Elementary School (M7CES).

Participant 6 is a single mother from Marbel 1 Central Elementary School. She has only 1 daughter who is studying at Marbel 1 Central elementary School. She is found to be very cooperative and active parent during the MDL.

Instruments

The researcher formulated an interview schedule as the instrument of this study. It is composed of seven (7) open-ended questions, asking about the experiences, challenges, and coping strategies of parents in the home learning of their children in the modular distance learning. Follow-up questions were asked aside from the major questions. The interview schedule was checked by graduate school professors and research experts at the NDMU. It was improved by changing some questions based on the recommendations of the experts.

Procedure

Permission to conduct the study was requested from the Department of Education (DepEd) officials of the Koronadal City Division. After the approval, coordination was done with the selected central schools, the school heads, and the grade 2 advisers to get their consent for the interviews of the parents. The key informant interviews were conducted in the central schools with the selected parents. Prior to the interview, the researcher explained what the research is all about and rapport questions were asked followed by the major questions in the interview guide. The standard research protocols were followed such as ensuring their anonymity in the entire research process, the confidentiality of the interview, and the manner of keeping and disposal of audio recordings. The researcher used a mix of English, Filipino, and Hiligaynon which are the medium of communication of the participants. All the interviews were conducted over three days. In the data gathering, the researcher asked the participants to read and sign the consent form, then they were asked to answer the questions based on their real experiences, after the interview. The researcher thanked the participants for allowing her to have an in-depth interview about the study.

Data Analysis

The study used thematic data analysis in describing the involvement of parents in the home learning of their children, the challenges they encountered and the coping strategies they employed during the modular learning modality. The processing and analysis of the Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) followed certain steps and procedures. The interviews were transcribed verbatim after each KII was finished. The transcriptions were read several times to make sense of them and cleaned them of unnecessary utterances or expressions of the participants. The coding was done by highlighting significant statements with assigned color highlights for easy arrangement of the concepts and themes: blue for the experiences of the parents are of three colors: blue for the roles, green for the support, and yellow for the strategies, red for the challenges and gray for the coping strategies on the challenges they faced. The highlighted statements were copy-pasted in the first column of a table for data analysis. Each Concepts were drawn out of the significant statements and then were grouped from which the themes emerged then were then discussed to describe the experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms.

Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the findings and the interpretation of the data. The significant statements, concepts, and themes were presented in each column per table. In analyzing the data gathered through KII process, textual analysis was done. Concepts were formed from the significant statements and then put into themes.

Experiences of parents in the home learning of their children during the modular distance learning. The involvement of parents is of three (3) aspects, such as (1) Roles, (2) Support, and (3) Strategies.

The tables below show the Experiences of Parents on their Involvement in the Home Learning of their Children as to their Roles, Support, Strategies, Challenges, and Coping Strategies on the challenges they faced during modular distance learning.

Table 1. *The Role of Parents in the Home Learning of Their Children*

<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Concepts</i>	<i>Themes</i>
Ang naging papel namin, kami ang naging second teachers...kung anu ang ah dapat e- lecture ng anu ng teacher... napunta sa amin... (P1.)	Second teacher at home	Delivering instruction
Ah yong sa akin kasi ma'am, ako ang nagtuturo sa kaniya, Ako ang nagtuturo ng modules niya, Parang teacher na rin, parang second teacher sa anak. (P3)	Facilitating learning at home	Facilitator of learning
Ginagabayan ko yong anak ko, kasi hindi pa po siya marunong magbasa po, ako po yong nagbabasa tapos siya nalang po yong sasagot. (P4.)	Guiding a non-reader learner.	
...binabasa ko po muna, tapos I explain ko sa kanya pag siya na po ang mag answer para matutu siya, yan po muna binabasa ko lahat ang questions tapos I translate ko po tapos siya na po ang mag answer ng kaniyang mga questions.	Reading and explaining the instructions to the learners first before they answer it.	Parents as a Model of Learning
Gintunan ko siya para magbasa Oo ginampanan ko, bilang teacher kag isa pud bilang nanay, kay obligasyon ko man I follow-up sa iya... Kag ang responsibilidad ng teacher kami ang nagsalo... (P5.)	Teaching Learners is an obligation of parents during the HLM.	Parents as a Reading Teacher
...tinitext kami ng mga ng adviser nila, na ready na yong modules nila, tapos kinukuha namin (P1.)	Teachers contact parents to receive modules.	Being the partner of the teacher in the distribution of the modules.
Opo schedule po ang pagkuha ng modules, ako ang nagakuha. (P2.)	The distribution of modules is scheduled.	
Ako po ang nagakuha ako on time, tapos balik ko man din on time kaya wla man ako trabaho siya lang. (P6.)	On time Receiving and returning of the modules	
Ang motivation ko sa kanya, sabi ko, magaral ka kasi pag face to face kawawa ka kapag hindi ka marunong magsagot sa teacher mo, or hindi marunong magbasa. Kaya natutu siya mag anu sa sarili nya. (P3.)	Motivating a non-reader to be a reader.	Motivator
Sinasabi ko po, na mag aral po para mag graduate may magandang trabaho sila, kasi wala man ako maibibigay na yaman atleast yong pagaaral nalang po. (P4.)	Instilling a good life in the future through education.	
...sige tapusin mo na, para marunong mag grade 2 ka marunong kana, tapos pagkatapos mo siling ko, may bilihin kita magkain tayo...(P6.)	Giving of Material things as a motivation.	
Gina guide sila para kung hindi nila alam... yong mga questions,gina guide ko po sila kung paano nila isagot ang kung anong tamang sagot po... (P2.)	Guiding learners in the modules	Parents as a Guide of their Children in Learning
Pinapaintindi ko po sa kaniya yong leksiyon...kagaya po nong sa math, sinasabi ko kung paano mag add mag minus. Pag s esp na po, sinasabi ko kung anu po ang magandang gawin yong tama at mali. (P4.)	Parents guided learners to do a task in the modules.	
...kagaya yong... sa mapah ata yon, yong dahoon tapos lagyan ng kulay, ako muna yong gagawa, tapos pag Nakita niya kung paano Gawain siya nalang gagawa, parang ganon. (P5.)	Guiding children by showing samples to do a task/activity.	
Gina guidan ko lang siya po, nang siya lang gahimo tapos naga guide lang ko sa iya,(P6)	Guiding learners while doing a task in the modules.	
...magpabili ng mga color or drawing book...ginabigay ko pero sabi ko sige basta tapusin mo ang answer sheets sa modules mo. (P3.)	Buying learning materials for learners to finish a task in the modules.	Provider
Sa paraan na anu ang mga needs niya, ...kung kailangan niya mga color...ah basta tanan nga kung anu ang kailangan sa modular binibigay ko sa kanya. (P3).	Providing the learners' needing materials	

It has been said that almost all the participants during the modular learning modality became second teachers automatically. This means they were the ones who did the things that the actual teachers were supposed to do inside the classrooms. Such as:

Delivering Instruction

On being a second teacher at home, parents were the ones who did the delivery of instructions to learners at home like what the teachers inside the classroom do. They were teaching the lessons in the modules in a way that the learners could understand it. They applied different strategies and motivations for learners to learn the lessons in the modules. They made all the possible ways to assist and guide their children in doing the performance tasks and activities in the modules. Manlangit et al. (2022) provide support for the idea that parents or guardians had a variety of roles in modular distance learning, such as curriculum deliverer, home innovator, module-ator, and bundy-clock. As said by participant 1, what the teachers were supposed to do inside the classroom were done by the parents at home as the second teacher:

Ang naging papel namin, kami ang naging second teachers...kung anu ang ah dapat e- lecture ng anu ng teacher... napunta sa amin... (P1.)

Parents as Facilitators of Learning

In facilitating learning, parents played lot of roles and one of those roles were providing the needed learning materials to learners for them to be motivated and inspired to learn, setting a conducive learning environment that is free from noise and distractions, following a daily time routine in teaching the modules to learners. Parents extended kinds of support and did different strategies in facilitating learning at home. This is in line with the research of Sari and Maningtyas (2020) that during the modular distance learning at home, parents were the facilitator of learning. They guide and assist their children in learning the lessons in the modules. Parents were the ones who taught and explained the content of the lessons in the modules. They provided samples for better understanding of the lesson. They assessed the learning outcomes of the children, and they checked the finished output.

Ah yong sa akin kasi ma'am, ako ang nagtuturo sa kaniya, Ako ang nagtuturo ng modules niya, Parang teacher na rin, parang second teacher sa anak. (P3)

Parents as a Model to their Children

To make sure that the performance tasks and activities in the modules would be completed by their children, parents showed how to do a task first before the learners do it themselves. They let their children watch them doing a task or activity and or they played video from YouTube on how to do a particular task or project in the modules. This is an effective way of teaching a first grader pupil. This is consistent with the study of Durisic and Bunijevac, (2017) that parents served as motivators of learners in doing all the tasks and activities in the modules. They also supplied all the needed learning materials for them to effectively learn the lessons in the modules. Parents were also the model of the children in learning in a way that parents showed the children on how to do a task first and then let the children do it by themselves. Due to restricted contact with teachers, the learners' parents or guardians will serve as their role models (Lebaste, 2020). According to Capulso et al. (2021) parents are the primary sources of inspiration and role models for their children. Children always adopt the values and behavioral patterns of their parents. Participant 4 did model approach:

Ginagabayan ko yong anak ko, kasi hindi pa po siya marunong magbasa po, ako po yong nagbabasa tapos siya nalang po yong sasagot. (P4.).

Parents as a Reading Teacher

Parents admitted to themselves that one of their main problems during the modular learning modality is about the level of their children in reading skills. Children were not able to go to school and be taught by their adviser the reading in a formal and effective way. So, during the modular learning modality they served as a reading teacher to their children. Parents gave importance in teaching reading to learners at home, it is one of the fundamental basic learning skills that a learner must possess.

Gintunan ko siya para magbasa Oo ginampanan ko, bilang teacher kag isa pud bilang nanay, kay obligasyon ko man I follow-up sa iya... Kag ang responsibilidad ng teacher kami ang nagsalo... (P5.)

During the modular distance learning, parents play a vital role in the learning progress of their children that the roles of teachers at school now transferred to them as they are now the ones who teach all the subject's areas to their children through the modules. This is supported by Manlangit, et al. (2022) that parents or guardians play many roles in modular distant learning, including module-ator, bundy-clock, the one delivering the instruction and home innovator. The learning progress and the academic performance of the children are now in their hands as parents. Parents' involvement affects their children's academic performance, according to Shute et al. (2011)'s conclusion. There were concerns that the improvement of students' academic performance was determined by the level of parents' involvement.

Being the Partner of the Teacher in the Distribution of the Modules

During the modular learning modality, Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) were the main source of learning. Parents or guardians were the ones who receive and return the modules in school. They must get and return the modules to teacher on time, because modules are time bounded wherein a learner must finish answering the activities in the modules within a week and submit them to have other modules for the next week. Before parents could get the SLMs, teachers must inform them. This is consistent with the study of Talimodao and Madrigal, (2021). Teachers and parents work together to educate their children. They assist and mentor students as they respond to the modular lessons they are sent during the modular learning process, acting as para-teachers and home facilitators (Manlangit, et al. 2020). The administrators' schedules will determine when parents and parents/guardians will retrieve the self-learning modules from the school (DepEd, 2020). Parents' schedules vary depending on the administrators' and guardians will take up the self-learning modules provided by the school (DepEd, 2020). Parents were the partners of teachers in teaching the children the modules. As cited by the participant 1:

...tinitext kami ng mga ng adviser nila, na ready na yong modules nila, tapos kinukuha namin (P1.)

In the distributions of SLMs, it was being distributed by the teachers by schedules wherein teachers inform the parents by text, chat or call to get the modules, and parents are required to get and return the modules on time. It is one of the roles of parents and guardian to do it.

Self-Learning Modules were being distributed by schedules; it must be received by the parents or guardians on time because it is a time bounded learning material. Participants of this study were very cooperative and active in getting the modules from school on its schedule as said by the participants 4:

Opo schedule po ang pagkuha ng modules, ako ang nagakuha (Participant 4.)

The modules must also be returned to teachers on time following the schedules. Upon returning them to teachers, the modules must be completely answered by the learners. Unemployed parents could get and return the SLMs on time as cited by participant 6.

Ako po ang nagakuha ako on time, tapos balik ko man din on time kaya wla man ako trabaho siya lang. (Participant 6.)

Motivator

During modular distance learning, one of the parent's primary tasks is to keep their child interested in learning when they participate in modular learning. This is in line with the findings of Jaiswal's (2017) study, which found that parents play a vital role in fostering their children's educational development by providing them with resources for learning and motivating them to succeed.

It has been proven that one of the great factors of the good performance of learners in school is the motivation of the parents. Learners are inspired and motivated to study and strive hard in accomplishing all the necessary documents in their school when their parents are motivating them. Parents were motivating the learners that they must be a reader; they must know how to read. They explained to them the importance of reading and that as grade 1 pupils they must be a reader when they enroll in grade 2. This is consistent with the study of Durisic and Bunijevac, (2017) that parents served as motivator of learners in doing all the tasks and activities in the modules. They also supplied all the needed learning materials for them to effectively learn the lessons in the modules. Parents were also the model of the children in learning in a way that parents showed the children on how to do a task first and then let the children do it by themselves. Participant 3 as cited:

Ang motivation ko sa kanya, sabi ko, magaral ka kasi pag face to face kawawa ka kapag hindi ka marunong magsagot sa teacher mo, or hindi marunong magbasa. Kaya natutu siya mag anu sa sarili nya. (P3.)

One of the motivations of parents to learners was telling the learners that the only best gift they could ever give their children is education. This was said by a participant.

...sige tapusin mo na, para marunong mag grade 2 ka marunong kana, tapos pagkatapos mo siling ko, may bilingin kita magkain tayo...

Also, parents motivated learners by giving material things as a reward for them to do good in the modules. Participant 6 said that she motivated her child to study hard and accomplish all the tasks in the modules, for him to be ready when the schooling is back to normal, so that when they are in grade 2, they will be able to do task by themselves.

Parents as Guide of the Children in Learning

Parents also served as guides to the children in teaching them the lesson in the modules. They guided the learners in a way that they showed to their children how to answer, or to do a particular task or activity in the modules; they do modeling. For example, in mathematics, they show them first how to solve a question or equation and then they let them do it after watching it. In making a project, they show first how to do it and then after, they would let their children do it by themselves, and when it comes to solving in math, parents explained and solved the problem before them. This is consistent with the study of Durisic and Bunijevac, (2017) that parents served as motivators of learners in doing all the tasks and activities in the modules. They also supplied all the needed learning materials for them to effectively learn the lessons in the modules. Parents were also the model of the children in learning in a way that parents showed the children how to do a task first and then let the children do it by themselves. As cited by participant 4:

Pinapaintindi ko po sa kaniya yong leksiyon kung anu po yon, kagaya po nong sa math, sinasabi ko kung paano mag add mag minus. Pag s esp na po, sinasabi ko kung anu po ang magandang gawin yong tama at mali. (Participant 4.)

For a learner to do a particular task in the modules, parents applied the I you do Approach, wherein the parents show how to do it first a particular project or task before the children do it, like what participant 5 said in her statement:

...kagaya yong... sa mapeh ata yon, yong dahoon tapos lagyan ng kulay, ako muna yong gagawa, tapos pag Nakita niya kung paano Gawain siya nalang gagawa, parang ganon. (P5.)

Parents told the learners the importance of accomplishing the tasks in the modules. They will not get a high grade if they do not complete answering worksheets and assessments in the modules as what participant 5 said. For a learner to do a particular task in the modules, parents applied the I you do Approach, wherein the parents show how to do it first a particular project or task before the children do it, like what participant 5 said in her statement:

On the other hand, parents also served as guides for learners in answering a test or a task in the modules. Learners needed the guidance of their parents in learning and answering the tests in the modules. Learners could not learn and do much on the modules without the assistance and guidance of their parents. Parents as guides were indeed important for the learners to learn the lessons in the modules, how they could properly answer a question and do performance tasks.

Gina guide sila para kung hindi nila alam... yong mga questions, gina guide ko po sila kung paano Nila isagot ang kung anong tamang sagot po... (P2.)

Table 2. The Support of Parents in the Home Learning of Their Children

<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Concepts</i>	<i>Themes</i>
Oras, yong Oras at saka yong pagtuturo sa sa anak, yong sa oras po. (P1).	Time was the number 1 support given by parents.	Giving time
Opo yong full time po ang support ko sa kanya , kasi para po yon sa school nila. (P2.)	Rendering full-time as support to children	
Wala ako trabaho, ang time ko ay para lang gid sa iya, naga laba ako, nagaluto ako kon aga, tapos luto pakainin ko siya, tapos ligo tapos mag module na kami. (P6.)	Plain housewife had a lot of time in teaching their children.	
...kung kailangan niya mga color or something, ah basta tanan nga kung anu ang kailangan sa modular binibigay ko sa kanya. (P3).	Learning materials like colors, drawing books and the like are important for grade 1 pupils.	Supplying the Needed Learning Materials
Tanan nga mga support na makaya ko lang. binigay ko. (P5).	Parents provided materials to learners that are available and affordable.	
...pero pag wala kaming time, naga hired kami ng anu ng tutor para sa anak namin para makahabol siya. (P1)	Busy parents hired tutors for their children.	
...nagpa help ako sa mga tutor na anu teacher, ...kasi kung kami mga parents kasi mayroon din mga obligation sa paghahanap buhay. (P).	Hiring tutors helped parents in teaching the children the modules.	Hiring of Tutors for Learners.
...may tutorial siya, anu lang siya 1-hour lang every Saturday. (P3).	Tutoring children for short periods of time.	

Giving Time

Time was the number 1 support given by almost all the parent-participants. Being a full-time housewife, participants 1 and 2 have given much of their in teaching their children the lessons modules, because they knew that it was their responsibility in teaching their children at home. Wang et al. (2020) state that a strong bond is commonly observed between parents and their children when they spend more time together, allowing them to collaborate more on the child's educational activities. It also says that parents who are more approachable and spend more time with their kids may help them realize that they are there for them when they need comfort and hope, which can lessen their suffering and anxiety.

Wala ako trabaho, ang time ko ay para lang gid sa iya, naga laba ako, nagaluto ako kon aga, tapos luto pakainin ko siya, tapos ligo tapos mag module na kami. (Participant 6.)

Participant 6 on being a non-working mother gave so much of her time in teaching her child the lessons in the modules. She immediately teaches her child after being done with the house chores.

Oras, yong Oras at saka yong pagtuturo sa sa anak, yong sa oras po. (Participant 1.)

Opo yong full time po ang support ko sa kanya, kasi para po yon sa school nila. (Participant 2.)

Supplying the Needed Learning Materials

The parents had to provide all the needs of their children for them to learn at home through modules. For early grades, learning materials are important in teaching them, for them to learn effectively. Parents provided learning materials like colors, drawing books and the like for the learners to easily grasp the lesson especially in learning letters, shapes, numbers etc. This is consistent with the study of Durisic and Bunijevac, (2017) that parents served as motivators of learners in doing all the tasks and activities in the modules. They also supplied all the needed learning materials for them to effectively learn the lessons in the modules. Parents were also the model of the children in learning in a way that parents showed the children on how to do a task first and then let the children do it by themselves as said by participant 3.

...kung kailangan niya mga color or something, ah basta tanan nga kung anu ang kailangan sa modular binibigay ko sa kanya. (P3).

Parent 5 also said that she had provided all the needs of her child in teaching her the modules so that she could effectively learn. Because once everything is well provided to the learners, she/he can easily learn and grasp the lesson you teach them because they are inspired and motivated. She provided all the available materials that she could provide just to ensure that her child would still learn despite the pandemic.

Tanan nga mga support na makaya ko lang. binigay ko. (Participant 5.)

This is in line with the findings of Jaiswal's (2017) study, which found that parents play a vital role in fostering their children's educational development by providing them with resources for learning and motivating them to succeed.

Hiring of Tutors for Learners.

It is given to all parents that they want their children to have quality education, despite the pandemic, parents really wanted to give their children quality education. One way of realizing this was to hire a tutor for their children as one of their supports in the learning of their children at home. Some parents are busy in their livelihood. So, for the working parent, they hired tutors just to guide, monitor, and teach their children the modules, As said by the participant 1:

...pero pag wala kaming time, naga ha-hired kami ng anu ng tutor para sa anak namin para makahabol siya. (Participant 1.)

Participant 3 said that she is not the only one who teaches her child the modules, but she also hired a tutor for her. She teaches her child during weekdays and the tutor teaches her child during weekends as for part-time tutoring.

...may tutorial siya, anu lang siya 1-hour lang every Saturday. anu lang siya 1- hour lang every Saturday. (Participant 3.)

Table 3. The Strategies of Parents in the Home Learning of Their Children

Significant Statements	Concepts	Theme
Gumagamit din kami ng anu, gumagamit din kami ng google. (P1).	Parents used Google to teach their children.	Utilization of YouTube and Google as Strategy
Youtube, ginapakita ko, ...or minsan sa google gina try ko open ang google, kung paano siya sa subject na halimbawa araling panlipunan makita din sa google, or sa youtube. (P3)	Parents showed learning videos to children in a particular subject on YouTube.	
Pag may mga talagang mahirap na hindi ko maintindihan, yong youtube talaga malaking tulong. (P4)	Lessons that are hard to discuss by parents, they find them on YouTube.	Using ABAKADA Unang Hakbang sa Pagbabasa Approach
...kung may mga kinanglanon ti di mag youtube, may mga di maintindihan kay mga project project dyan sa modules, mag anu kami youtube... (P5).	Parents let their children watch YouTube while doing a project or performance task in the modules.	
Yong anu abakada approach, Opo, kasi sa sound kasi eh, Madali lang yang abakada na yan. (P2.)	Teaching reading Using ABAKADA Unang Hakbang sa Pagbabasa Approach.	Translating the Hiligaynon/English words to Tagalog or vice versa.
...unang una na step nya, sympre mag umpisa gid sa abakada, tapos two letter two letter ung syllable ba, ana ba tapos dugtongan ko naman, anu ni anu ni pagbasa... (P5).	Teaching reading to children, starting from syllables using ABAKADA Unang Hakbang sa Pagbabasa Approach	
...pag hindi po niya maintindihan in tagalog, ini Ilonggo ko po, kasi Hiligaynon po yong subject nila, ...pag hindi niya po ma catch up translate ko po sa tagalog, pag hindi na po Ilonggo nanaman. (P4).	Translating the Filipino to Hiligaynon words for the learners to understand.	Giving of Extrinsic Rewards
...pag English ang anu dapat mabal-an niya in tagalog, tapos siling ko dapat maintindihan mo kag bal-an mo kung anu ang ibigsabihin pag sa English bal-an mo sa tagalog, gina translate ko sa iya... (P5)	Translating the Hiligaynon/English words to Filipino for the learners to understand.	
Pag yung English pag hind niya naintindihan I tatagalog ko nalang po, o kaya li Ilonggo ko nalang po para mas maintindihan niya. (P).	Translating the English words to Filipino or Ilonggo for the learners to understand.	Instilling in the Children the Importance of Education.
...may bilingin kita magkain tayo, nang ganyan ganyan kasi bata talaga mam eh, sige ah siling niya basta ha nag promise ka. (P6).	Motivating learners as a child by using extrinsic reward.	
...magsabi siya magpabili ng mga color or drawing book or something, ginabigay ko pero sabi ko sige basta taposin mo ang answer sheets sa modules mo. (P3).	Giving material rewards to children for answering worksheets in the modules.	Instilling in the Children the Importance of Education.
...kung time na magpadala ang iya nga daddy, ...mangayo ko sang amu sini, oh sige baklan taka basta mag eskwela ka tarong. (P5).	Learners ask for material rewards from parents after having answered the activities in the modules.	
Ang motivation ko sa kanya, sabi ko, magaral ka kasi pag face to face kawawa ka kapag hindi ka marunong magsagot sa teacher mo, or hindi marunong magbasa. Kaya natutu siya mag anu sa sarili nya. (P3)	Reminding learners to strive hard in learning reading in preparation for face-to-face class.	Parents Told the learners that the only best thing they can give them is education.
Sinasabi ko po, na mag aral po para mag graduate may magandang trabaho sila, kasi wala man ako maibibigay na yaman atleast yong pagaaral nalang po. (P5).	Parents Told the learners that the only best thing they can give them is education.	

Utilization of YouTube and Google as Strategy

Since parents act as their children's teachers at home and they did not know much of the strategies to use in teaching a lesson, and to make it easy for them to teach and guide their children in learning the modules, they made use of the technology by using YouTube and google in teaching them. As said by participant 1 that she used YouTube in teaching her child.

Gumagamit din kami ng anu, gumagamit din kami ng google. (P1).

Watching a demo lecture on YouTube was one of the strategies of parents in teaching their children. She showed a particular topic or lesson to her child from the YouTube video for her child to understand it better. Insorio and Macandog (2022) claim that when paired with module lessons, video lessons help students understand concepts. Students appreciated watching YouTube videos because they could observe the teacher demonstrating the subject.

Youtube, ginapakita ko, ...or minsan sa google gina try ko open ang google, kung paano siya sa subject na halimbawa araling panlipunan makita din sa google, or sa youtube. (P3)

Based on the statements of the participants 4 and 5, in teaching their children the modules, they utilized the YouTube for effective teaching, wherein they let the child watch videos from YouTube discussing a particular topic, and when there are things that they found out to be difficult, they search for them on google. In making the required project in the modules, parents let their child watch it on YouTube as a guide. Following are their statements:

Pag may mga talagang mahirap na hindi ko maintindihan, yong youtube talaga malaking tulong. (P4)

...kung may mga kinanglanon ti di mag youtube, may mga di maintindihan kay mga project project dyan sa modules, mag anu kami youtube... (P5).

Using ABAKADA Unang Hakbang sa Pagbabasa Approach.

Teaching reading by sound was one of the strategies of the participant 2 in teaching reading to her child. She used the ABAKADA Unang Hakbang sa Pagbabasa approach in teaching it to her child. She started teaching her child the sound of the letters. It was important for them to focus on teaching their children how to read first aside from teaching them other lessons in the modules though it is a challenge because of being not trained.

Yong anu abakada approach, Opo, kasi sa sound kasi eh, Madali lang yang abakada na yan. (Participant 2.)

Participant 5 said that in teaching her child reading she started teaching him syllable by syllable until the child could read at least one word.

...unang una na step nya, sympre mag umpisa gid sa abakada, tapos two letter two letter ung syllable ba, ana ba tapos dugtongan ko naman, anu ni anu ni pagbasa... (Participant 5.)

Translating the Hiligaynon or English words to Filipino or Vice Versa.

In the modules for grade 1 to 3, the medium of instructions used in the modules are Mother Tongue or the Hiligaynon in this place it is one of the challenges they encountered by parents in the modules. Due to that problem, the strategy of parents in teaching the children was that they translated the Hiligaynon words to Filipino and vice versa just to make sure that their children would be able to understand it. This is like the study of Talimodao, and Madrigal, (2021) which stated that parents use their mother tongue as a medium of instruction to better communicate their ideas and explain concepts to their children, and parents translate the lessons to Filipino for their children to understand and answer what is indicated in their module. This bears similarity with the study of Luaña (2021), who stated that many subject areas used English as the medium of instruction in writing the modules; thus, parents translate the lessons to Filipino content for their child's better understanding of the module. Moreover, parents also guide their children by explaining and giving examples without explicitly giving them the answers, thereby acting as a guide on the side, allowing their children to participate in the learning process actively. Parents were using their mother tongue in teaching their children the modules as said by participant 4.

...pag hindi po niya maintindihan in tagalog, ini Ilonggo ko po, kasi Hiligaynon po yong subject nila, pag sa kuya na po pag sa English, pag hindi niya po ma catch up translate ko po sa tagalog, pag hindi na po Ilonggo nanaman. (Participant 4.)

Parents could not easily understand it even though some of them are pure Ilonggo. because of the deep Hiligaynon words used in the modules, for them to address that problem, for the English, they needed to translate it Filipino or Ilonggo for their children to understand it. This is also anchored on the study Luaña (2021) as cited by Gumapac, et al. (2021) which found that parents experience difficulties when their children struggle to read and comprehend literature written in English. For their children to comprehend the lessons and respond to the questions in their module, parents translate the courses into Filipino.

...pag English ang anu dapat mabal-an niya in tagalog, tapos siling ko dapat maintindihan mo kag bal-an mo kung anu ang ibigsabihin pag sa English bal-an mo sa tagalog, gina translate ko sa iya... (Participant 5.)

Pag yung English pag hind niya naintindihan I tagalog ko nalang po, o kaya Ii Ilonggo ko nalang po para mas maintindihan niya. (Participant.)

Giving of Extrinsic Rewards

Giving extrinsic rewards was one of the strategies that parents gave in teaching the learners at home through the modules, they gave extrinsic rewards like, buying foods for the learners. It was important for learners who are in grade 1, for them to be motivated and inspired in learning. As cited by participant 6:

Tapos pagkatapos mo siling ko, may bilihin kita magkain tayo, nang ganyan ganyan kasi bata talaga mam eh, sige ah siling niya basta ha nag promise ka... (Participant 6.)

The giving of learning materials as an extrinsic reward was also done by the parents in teaching their children at home. They promise to their child to give them they want like colors, drawing books after completing answering the modules. It has been proven that both intrinsic and extrinsic rewards are important and needed in teaching, especially when you are teaching children in lower grades. In the context of education, motivation aids in helping kids and teenagers concentrate on a main objective or result.

As parents 3 and 5 said that one of their strategies in teaching their children the modules was the use of extrinsic rewards in which they gave material incentives or rewards to their children every time they performed well in the modules. They found it effective to use when you are teaching young age like children.

...magsabi siya magpabili ng mga color or drawing book or something, ginabigay ko pero sabi ko sige basta taposin mo ang answer sheets sa modules mo. (Participant 3.)

...kung time na magpadala ang iya nga daddy, kay ara man sa ga ubra, mang mangayo ko sang amu sini, oh sige baklan taka basta mag eskwela ka tarong. (Participant 5.)

Instilling in the Children the Importance of Having Education

One of the participants said that one of her strategies in teaching her children is by giving him advice that education is one of the important things in this world. She gave a life's lesson to her son that she wanted her son to study hard to have a good future by having a good job. She does not want her son to be like them having no work because they only graduated in elementary. She instilled in her son the importance of education. And she told her son that you can only achieve education if he focus and studies hard. In the result of the study of Friales, Quemado, and Bayog (2022), it is common among parents that one of their strategies in encouraging and motivating their children to learn or to study hard is by instilling in them the importance of education. As participant 5 said:

Sinasabi ko po, na mag aral po para mag graduate may magandang trabaho sila, kasi wala man ako maibibigay na yaman atleast yong pagaaral nalang po. (Participant 5.)

As Li and Qiu (2018) emphasized, children's motivation to learn is less the lower the family's socioeconomic status. Their learning behavior increases engagement as parents become more interested in their child's education. Like this, a child's environment has a significant influence on children's well-being. For children to develop, learn, and explore, their home must be secure and healthy.

Sabi ko, magaral ka kasi pag face to face kawawa ka kapag hindi ka marunong magsagot sa teacher mo, or hindi marunong magbasa. Kaya natutu siya mag anu sa sarili nya. (Participant 3.)

Participant 3 motivated her son to pursue education by telling him that he needed to be a reader in preparation for grade 2 so that when he is grade 2, he can already read.

Table 4. *The Challenges of Parents on their Involvement in the Home Learning of their Children*

<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Concepts</i>	<i>Themes</i>
...pag nagtatanong ang mga anak namin na papa mama ito yong nasa modules, so sympre sa katagalan ng panahon na pinag aralan din namin so sympre makakalimutan natin yan, so yon ang mga hamon sa amin sa mga parents...(P1).	Parents have no sufficient knowledge on the lessons in the modules.	Insufficient knowledge of Parents
Mahirap, kasi mahirap kasi po yong mga bata naano sa laro, kasi pag uras po ng pagtuturo nagmamadalli po sila na matapos para maglaro nanaman sila ulit, kaya mahirap sila anuhin, Kasi yong teacher mas Madali sila, pero yong nanay paligoyligoy pa sila. (P2).	Difficulty in maintaining the attention of the children.	
...kung ka isa mam hindi ko maintindihan ang questions...kung isa hindi ko man maintindihan...(P6)	Parents find it hard to understand the questions in the modules.	Difficulty in understanding the Hiligaynon/English words.
So far, yong challenges lang naming yong anu yong ah yong third language, ng mga yong yong mga yong sa Ilonggo, yon yong anu, Kasi hindi namin medjo maintindihan ung mga malalim na mga Ilonggo... (P1).	Parents have difficulty in understanding deep Hiligaynon words in the modules, because it is not their native language.	
Minsan sa Hiligaynon, kasi ang Hiligaynon kay malalim masyado ang mga tanong sa Hiligaynon, ako Ilonggo din ako, pero minsan hindi ko rin maintindihan minsan ung mga tanong. (P3)	Even those parents who are Ilonggo or Illongo have the same difficulty in understanding deep Hiligaynon words in the modules.	Difficulty in accomplishing the performance task.
Nabudlayan ko gid ma'am, kay diba sa Hiligaynon, mostly abi tagalog man ta, ti budlay gid magpaintindi sa bata. (P5)	It is hard for the parents to explain to the children the lessons in the modules stated in Hiligaynon.	Financial difficulty
Yong mga projects niya na mga anu, mga halimbawa may request sa modules na gagawin itong mga ganyan. So diko Madali dali yan ma anu ma gawa. (P2).	Unaccomplished projects or performance tasks in the modules due to unavailability of materials.	Difficulty in time management
	Financial problems were one of the challenges of	

<p>Financial, haha. una yong financial, pangalawa yong time management. (P3). ...yong pag-aaral po nila, sympre ako po nanay may trabaho po sa bahay, sympre medjo hassle, pero kya naman po, time management, pag gusto mo turuan ang anak mo, bigyan mo ng panahon... (P5). Oo sa bahay lang maam, tapos amu lang na mga kalaban niya mga trabaho sa bahay, pero pwede man na, karon lang. importatnte na makatoun ang bata. (P4). ...nahirapan ko po sa pagbasa po don sa grade 1... parang mahirap po I kwan yong parent ka parang hindi siya makinig, unlike sa teacher na parang matakot siya. (P4).</p> <p>Sympre, naga module, unahon ko kay hindi pa man siya kayo kabalo magbasa. (P5). Yong hindi marunong magbasa, yan talaga mahirap sa mga bata, totoo po yan, kasi explain mo sa kanila ganyan ganyan. (P2). Opo, kay mga maliit ang letter sa modules, maliit pa siya maam hindi ko makita. (P6).</p>	<p>some parents during HLM.</p> <p>Managing time between house chores and teaching children the modules.</p> <p>Teaching the children must be a priority over doing the household chores. The main problem of parents during the MDL is that their children are non-readers. And they find it hard to teach their children to read because the children don't listen to them. Parents give importance to teaching reading to their children.</p> <p>Parents admitted that it is very hard to teach non-reader learners. Small font of texts in the modules as a challenge for parents.</p>	<p>Difficulty in teaching a non-reader.</p> <p>Difficulty in reading text printed in small font size.</p>
--	---	---

Insufficient Knowledge

Difficulty in facilitating learning or insufficient knowledge of parents was one of the challenges encountered by parents. The reasons were sometimes they did not have enough knowledge on a particular topic or lesson because of not being a teacher, and they could not directly answer the learners when they about that lesson. This is also like the findings of the study of Bonilla, A. H. (2022) that parents have difficulty in facilitating their children at home due to lack of knowledge of the content. This was said by participant 1:

...pag nagtatanong ang mga anak namin na papa mama ito yong nasa modules, so sympre sa katagalan ng panahon na pinag aralan din namin so sympre makakalimutan natin yan, so yon ang mga hamon sa amin sa mga parents...(P1).

Another challenge they encountered was that they found it hard to teach the learners at home because learners do not take seriously believing that parents are not real teachers. Parents realized that the tasks of teachers are not that easy to do, and they also noticed the difference of teachers and parents in teaching the children that when they are the one who is teaching their children, they do not really focus in listening at their discussion. Parents found it hard to teach their children the modules all throughout the year, but because they are determined for their children to learn despite the pandemic, they did their best to teach all the lessons in the modules. It reminds that early grade levels need to be closely supervised by parents in the lessons. However, despite the efforts to assist parents in this daunting task of educating their children at home, struggles are inevitable (Garbe et al., 2020).

Mahirap, kasi mahirap kasi po yong mga bata naano sa laro, kasi pag uras po ng pagtuturo nagmamadalli po sila na matapos para maglaro nanaman sila ulit, kaya mahirap sila anuhin, Kasi yong teacher mas Madali sila, pero yong nanay paligoyligoy pa sila. (Participant 5.)

Difficulty in Understanding the Hiligaynon or English Words in the Modules.

From the different point of view of the participants of this study about the challenges they experienced on modular distance learning, almost all of them answered that the main challenge they experienced in the modules is the Hiligaynon words or sentences that were used in the modules. Given the fact that in lower grades like grade 1, the medium of instructions they used in the modules is the Mother Tongue which is the Hiligaynon in this place and for some parents it is their third language. There are words and sentences stated in deep Hiligaynon dialect which they could not understand. So, in this case, it was really a challenge for them because they were not able to teach those lessons to their children. Someone cannot teach something which he or she doesn't know. This is also anchored on the study Luaña (2021) as cited by Gumapac, et al. (2021) which found that parents experience difficulties when their children struggle to read and comprehend literature written in English. For their children to understand the lessons and respond to the questions in their module, parents translate the courses into Filipino.

Participant 1 said that Hiligaynon is their third language so, it was hard for them to understand it and could not easily teach the lesson stated in Hiligaynon to the children.

So far, yong challenges lang namin yong anu yong ah yong third language, ng mga yong yong mga yong sa Ilonggo, yon yong anu, Kasi hindi namin medjo maintindihan ung mga malalim na mga Ilonggo... (Participant 1.)

For other parents, although they are Ilonggo, there were still deep Hiligaynon words used in the modules which they could not understand. Like what the participant 3 stated:

Minsan sa Hiligaynon, kasi ang Hiligaynon kay malalim masyado ang mga tanong sa Hiligaynon, ako Ilonggo din ako, pero minsan

hindi ko rin maintindihan minsan ung mga tanong. (Participant 3.)

As Filipino, we are used to speak Filipino Language at all times compared to Hiligaynon, so, some parents found it hard to speak and understand Hiligaynon in teaching their children the modules as said by participant 5 below:

Nabudlayan ko gid ma'am, kay diba sa Hiligaynon, mostly abi tagalog man ta, ti budlay gid magpaintindi sa bata. Participant 5.

Difficulty in Accomplishing the Performance Task

In the modules, there are also performance tasks, wherein learners need to accomplish that, like doing project or performing a task in doing a project, sometimes there are no availability of materials at home, and parents find it hard to help learners accomplish that performance task in the modules. This is also in line with the result of the study of Dangle, and Sumaoang, (2020, November) that because of the limited resources of at home pupils found it hard to accomplish or comply all the performance tasks in the modules as stated by the participant 2.

Yong mga projects niya na mga anu, mga halimbawa may request sa modules na gagawin itong mga ganyan. So diko Madali dali yan ma anu ma gawa. (Participant 2.)

Financial Difficulty

Out of six (6) participants of this study, participant 3 was the only ones who said that one of the challenges she faced during the pandemic was financial problems. It is opposite with the study of Agaton and Cueto (2021). While distance learning minimizes the spending priority of the family in terms of child's daily allowance, online learning gives additional financial burden for the family from the connection to the internet as it increases the use of electricity. However, because of the frequent loss of connection resulting in their withdrawal from the online session, students find it difficult to complete the activities during power outages.

Financial, haha. una yong financial, pangalawa yong time management. (Participant 3.)

Difficulty in Time Management

One of the challenges faced by the participants as cited by participant 4 was the time management. As much as they want to spend all their day and nighttime in teaching their children the modules, but they could not do so because of other things to do like house chores and some important things to do outside the house. They must be fair with their time that they had to do their obligations as father or mother in the family and at the same time they had to teach, guide, and assist the children in teaching them the modules. In other words, they must manage their time very well. Same result is true with the study of Cahapay (2021) that time management was one of the main problems of parents during the home learning of their parents during the modular distance modality. As parent 4 and 5 said:

Oo sa bahay lang maam, tapos amu lang na mga kalaban niya mga trabaho sa bahay, pero pwede man na, karon lang. importatnte na makatoun ang bata. -participant 4.

Participant 5 said that she spent much of her time teaching her child the modules than doing house chores, because she really wanted her child to learn the lessons in the modules.

...yong pag-aaral po nila, sympre ako po nanay may trabaho po sa bahay, sympre medjo hassle, pero kya naman po, time management, pag gusto mo turuan ang anak mo, bigyan mo ng panahon. (Participant 5.)

Participant 5 also said that she is teaching reading first to her child because her child did not know how to read.

...nahirapan ko po sa pagbasa po don sa grade 1 kasi kinder module tapos sa grade 1 modules, mahirap po sila turuan pag sa pagbasa po, tulad ng ba be bi, parang mahirap po I kwan yong parent ka parang hindi siya makinig, unlike sa teacher na parang matakot siya. (Participant 4.)

Sympre, naga module, unahon ko kay hindi pa man siya kayo kabalo magbasa (Participant 5.)

Participant 2 emphasized the importance of teaching reading to the learner at an early grade, because once a learner is a non-reader it is hard to teach them the other subject areas.

Difficulty in Reading Small Letters in the Modules.

Among the six (6) participants, one of them said that one of her challenges on the modules was the small font size of the text used in the modules. Participant 6 stated that sometimes she could not read the letter font in the modules printed in small font size. Same findings with the study of Bayucca, (2021) that one of the challenges of parents during modular home learning modality was the difficulty reading the small letters in the modules. Also, the study of Abelardo, et.al., 2019 revealed that as to the quality of printed modules, the figures are not appropriate, there are items that are not readable and some colors.

Opo, kay mga maliit ang letter sa modules, maliit pa siya maam hindi ko makita. (Participant 6.)

This is also anchored on the study Luaña (2021) as cited by Gumapac, et al. (2021) which found that parents experience difficulties when their children struggle to read and comprehend literature written in English. Parents translate the courses into Filipino so that their kids can understand the lessons and answer the questions in their module.

Participant 1 said that YouTube and Google are very helpful in teaching his child the lessons in the modules, aside from the tutor of his child they also made use of YouTube and Google to effectively teach his child. While participant 3 also used YouTube by letting her child watch a video lesson on YouTube. Same thing with participant 5 that she also used YouTube when making a project I the modules.

Gumagamit din kami ng anu, gumagamit din kami ng google. Sa teacher, tapos sa tutor nila, yong gadget ngayon, nakatulong din, nakatulong din ang gadget. (Participant.)

Naga Google din, youtube, kasi makita man sa youtube yong mga anu ng deped dati, parehas sa modules makita siya. (Participant 3.)

Oo mam, tapos kung may mga kinanglanon ti di mag youtube, may mga di maintindihan kay mga project project dyan sa modules, mag anu kami youtube, ay mang amuni, ana siya, siling ko, kay bright man ni sa youtube. (Participant 5.)

Applying self-initiated Interventions

After all the challenges that parents encountered during the home learning of their children during the module distance learning, one of their coping strategies is applying their self-initiated interventions. They are practical and creative in giving interventions to those challenges. As participant 5 said that once the needed materials for a task are not available, she was being creative by finding another way for the learners to do the task. This is like the result of the study of Friaies, Quemado, and Bayog, (2022) that parents used or developed their facilitative skill in mentoring and teaching their children just like what teachers do in the class.

Ginagawaan ko ng paraan, pag hindi ako makakita ng mga anu dina drawing ko nalang, para-anu, gina drawing ko nalang tapos gina cut ko. (Participant 5.)

Tinutulongan ko po, kagaya ng may ung sa kanilang, hindi ko alam sa mapeh ata yon, yong dahoon tapos lagyan ng kulay, ako muna yong gagawa, tapos pag Nakita niya kung paano Gawain siya nalang gagawa, parang ganon. (Participant)

Conclusions

As we all know parental involvement is one of the great factors that affect the learning development and academic performance of a child. Whatever learning modality that a learner is practicing be it face-to-face class, modular learning and online learning parental involvement is greatly needed. Learners are being motivated and inspired to learn and do better in school if they know that their parents keep an eye on them. This study is of big help for the parents whose children are studying modular learning modality because it revealed the roles, strategies, and support that the participants of the study used effectively and efficiently in teaching the children the lessons in the modules and in guiding them in answering the activities and performance tasks in the modules. If parents wanted their children to be academically competent, then they may also do the same roles, strategies, and support like the participants of the study did. This study implied the following: During the modular distance learning, parents should have high involvement to the learning process of the children, that parents should paly many roles in teaching the learners, they should give any means of support to learners for them to learn the lessons in the modules, they should make of use strategies in teaching the learners the lessons in the modules.

Participants of the study played roles like: parents served as the ones who get the modules in school; they were the ones delivering the instructions; facilitator of learning; they were the motivators for the learners to do all the tasks in the modules, and they were the providers of the additional needed learning materials of the learners.

Schools could encourage the parents involve themselves actively in the home learning of their children even after modular distance learning. They may adapt the strategies of the parent-participants in the study to the teaching of children at home.

References

- Agaton, C. B., & Cueto, L. J. (2021). Learning at Home: Parents' Lived Experiences on Distance Learning during COVID-19 Pandemic in the Philippines. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 10(3), 901-911.
- Agayon, A. J. D., Agayon, A. K. R., & Pentang, J. (2022). Teachers in the new normal: Challenges and coping mechanisms in secondary schools. *Journal of Humanities and Education Development (JHED)*, 4.
- Al-Mahrooqi, R., Denman, C., & Al-Maamari, F. (2016). Omani parents' involvement in their children's English education. *Sage Open*, 6(1), 2158244016629190.
- Altschul, I. (2011). Parental involvement and the academic achievement of Mexican American youths: what kinds of involvement in youths' education matter most?. *Social Work Research*, 35(3), 159-170.
- Antipkina, I., & Ludlow, L. H. (2020). Parental involvement as a holistic concept using Rasch/Guttman scenario scales. *Journal of Psychoeducational Assessment*, 38(7), 846-865.

- A Bayucca, S. (2021). Challenges encountered and technical assistance needed by parents and learners utilizing modular distance learning: Basis for a proposed support program. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 128-135.
- Bacatan, J., Suico, H. V., Olila, R., & Macatuay, A. (2022). Parents' level of engagement in the modular distance learning of elementary school students.
- Bacomo, A. C. C., Daculap, L. P., Ocampo, M. G. O., Paguaia, C. D., Pentang, J., & Bautista, R. M. (2022). Modular learning efficiency: Learner's attitude and performance towards self-learning modules.
- Bartolome, M. T., Mamat, N., & Masnan, A. H. (2017). Parental Involvement in the Philippines: A Review of Literatures. *International Journal of Early Childhood Education and Care*, 6, 41-50
- Beghetto, R. A. (2001). Virtually in the middle: Alternative avenues for parental involvement in middle-level schools. *The Clearing House*, 75(1), 21-25.
- Bonilla, M. T., Camo, J. G., Lanzaderas, R. A., Lanzaderas, R. A., & Bonilla, A. H. (2022). Parental involvement in a child's education at home during COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Humanities and Education Development (IJHED)*, 4(3), 6-13.
- Bower, H. A., & Griffin, D. (2011). Can the Epstein model of parental involvement work in a high-minority, high-poverty elementary school? A case studies. *Professional School Counseling*, 15(2), 2156759X1101500201.
- Bunijevac, M. & Đurišić, M., & (2017). Parental involvement is a important factor for successful education. *Center for Educational Policy Studies Journal*, 7(3), 137-153.
- Cahapay, M. B. (2021). Involvement of parents in remote learning of children amid COVID-19 crisis in the Philippines: A transcendental phenomenology. *International Journal of Sociology of Education*.
- Castroverde, F., & Acala, M. (2021). Modular distance learning modality: Challenges of teachers in teaching amid the Covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 10(8), 7-15.
- Ceka, A., & Murati, R. (2016). The Role of Parents in the Education of Children. *Journal of Education and practice*, 7(5), 61-64.
- Dangle, Y. R. P., and Sumaoang, J. D. (2020, November). The implementation of modular distance learning in the Philippine secondary public schools. In *3rd International Conference on Advanced Research in Teaching and Education (Vol. 100, p. 108)*.
- Department of Education (DepEd), Tria, J. Z. (2020). The COVID-19 pandemic through the lens of education in the Philippines: The new normal. *International Journal of Pedagogical Development and Lifelong Learning*, 1(1), 2-4.
- Durisc and Bunijevac, 2017). Durisc, M., and Bunijevac, M. (2017). Parental Involvement as an Important Factor for Successful Education *CEPS Journal*].
- Epstein model of parental involvement work in a high-minority, high-poverty elementary school? A case studies. *Professional School Counseling*, 15(2), 2156759X1101500201.
- Friales, W. C., Quemado, L. G., & Bayog, S. B. (2022). Home learning facilitation of parents on their children in the modular learning modality. *International Journal of Qualitative Research*, 1(3), 211-220.
- Gumapac, J. R., Aytona, E. M., & Alba, M. G. R. (2021). Parents involvement in accomplishing students learning tasks in the new normal. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 4(7), 367-380.
- Gloria, A., Neukamm, S., & Otto, F. (2020). A regularity theory for random elliptic operators. *Milan journal of mathematics*, 88, 99.
- Haiyudi, S. A. I., & Art-In, S. (2021). PARENTS' INVOLVEMENT IN LEARNING ASSESSMENT DURING REMOTE LEARNING IN PANDEMIC ERA. *Jurnal Kajian Teknologi Pendidikan*, 4(1)
- Henderson, A. T., & Berla, N. (1994). A new generation of evidence: The family is critical to student achievement.
- Jaiswal, S. K., & Choudhuri, R. (2017). A review of the relationship between parental involvement and students' academic performance. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 4(3), 110-123.
- Kwatubana, S., and Makhalemele, T. (2015). Parental involvement in the process of implementation of the National School Nutrition Programme in Public Schools. *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, 9(3), 315-323.
- Lawrence, K. C., & Fakuade, O. V. (2021). Parental Involvement, Learning Participation and Online Learning Commitment of Adolescent Learners during the COVID-19
- Lilawati and Sari, D. K., and Maningtyas, R. T. (2020, November). Parents' involvement in distance learning during the covid-19 pandemic. In *2nd Early Childhood and Primary Childhood Education (ECPE 2020) (pp. 94-97)*. Atlantis Press.
- Luaña, J. P. (2021). Why do parents answer their children's modules? A closer Look on parental practices and challenges in modular

- distance learning. *International Journal of Global Community*, 4(1-March), 1-16.
- Mamat, N., & Masnan, A. H. (2017). Parental Involvement in the Philippines: A Review of Literatures. *International Journal of Early Childhood Education and Care*, 6, 41-50.
- Magouirk, T. A. (2015). A correlational study of parental involvement at the elementary school, during COVID-19 pandemic: A developing country context. *European Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Education*, 2(2), e02109.
- Manlangit, A. C. P. (2022). The Challenges of Technical and Vocational Livelihood (TVL) Education in the New Normal as Perceived by Teachers in Biñan City Senior High School–San Antonio Campus. *Biñan City Senior High School–San Antonio Campus*.
- Masalimova, A. R., Khvatova, M. A., Chikileva, L. S., Zvyagintseva, E. P., Stepanova, V. V., & Melnik, M. V. (2022, March). Distance learning in higher education during COVID-19. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 7, p. 120). *Frontiers*.
- Meyer, J.L. "Impact of family process and status variables on student academic achievement." (2001).
- Misirli, O., & Ergulec, F. (2021). Emergency remote teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic: Parents experiences and perspectives. *Education and information technologies*, 26(6), 6699-6718
- Niehaus, K., & Adelson, J. L. (2014). School support, parental involvement, and academic and social-emotional outcomes for English language learners. *American Educational Research Journal*, 51(4), 810-844
- Nkoane 2020 Bonilla, M. T., Camo, J. G., Lanzaderas, R. A., Lanzaderas, R. A., & Bonilla, A. H. (2022). Parental involvement in a child's education at home during COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Humanities and Education Development (IJHED)*, 4(3), 6-13.
- Pimentel-Tibon, J. (2020). The new normal in basic education. *Lexology* <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx>.
- Ratih, K., & Sutopo, A. (2021). Peningkatan Motivasi Belajar Peserta Didik melalui Bimbel pada Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *Jurnal Ilmiah Kampus Mengajar*, 70-77.
- Rohayani, F. (2020). Menjawab Problematika yang Dihadapi Anak Usia Dini di Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *Qawwam*, 14(1), 29-50.
- Reuge, N., Jenkins, R., Brossard, M., Soobrayan, B., Mizunoya, S., Ackers, J., ... & Taulo, W. G. (2021). Education response to COVID 19 pandemic, a special issue proposed by UNICEF: Editorial review. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 87, 102485.
- Sadeghi, M. (2019). A shift from classroom to distance learning: Advantages and limitations. *International Journal of Research in English Education*, 4(1), 80-88.
- Sapungan, G. M., & Sapungan, R. M. (2014). Parental involvement in a child's education: Importance, barriers, and benefits. *Asian Journal of Management Sciences & Education*, 3(2), 42-48.
- Sari, D. K., & Maningtyas, R. T. (2020). Parents' involvement in distance learning during the covid-19 pandemic. *Proceedings of the 2nd Early Childhood and Primary Childhood Education*, 487, 94-97.
- Schleicher, A. (2020). The impact of COVID-19 on education: Insights from education at a glance 2020. Retrieved from oecd.org website: <https://www.oecd.org/education/the-impact-of-covid-19-on-education-insights-education-at-a-glance-2020.pdf>.
- Stufflebeam, D.L., 1983. The CIPP model for program evaluation. In *Evaluation models* (pp. 117-141). Springer, Dordrecht.
- Talimodao, A. J. S., & Madrigal, D. V. (2021). Printed modular distance learning in Philippine public elementary schools in time of COVID-19 pandemic: Quality, implementation, and challenges. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 4(3), 19-29.
- Touloupis, T. (2021). Parental involvement in homework of children with learning disabilities during distance learning: Relations with fear of COVID-19 and resilience. *Psychology in the Schools*, 58(12), 2345-2360.
- Unesco, I. (2020). Basic texts of the 2003 convention for the safeguarding of the intangible cultural heritage.
- Waters, E., ... & Campbell, R. (2014). The WHO Health Promoting School framework for improving the health and well-being of students and their academic achievement. *Cochrane database of systematic reviews*, (4).
- Wu, M. Y., Zhai, J., Wall, G., & Li, Q. C. (2021). Understanding international students' motivations to pursue higher education in mainland China. *Educational Review*, 73(5), 580-596.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Asmirah G. Abdulrahman
Marbel 1 Central Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines